

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Report on the contribution to standardization

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Executive Summary

This document is based on the conclusions of D8.5 'Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards' that included the information on the relevant existing and ongoing standards and the relevant standardization technical committees to facilitate the use of existing knowledge and the compatibility and the interoperability of the ECOBULK developments and thus facilitate the acceptance and utilization by the market of the developed solutions.

The contribution to standardization seeks to transfer selected results of ECOBULK to standards. The extrapolation of the outputs of this project to standards that are widely recognized by the industry and that are developed in a system external to the Consortium will ease the market uptake of these results and their impact beyond the duration of the project. The standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel towards the stakeholders represented in the standardization technical committees. The main disseminated results of this project are the CWA documents prepared by the consortium. Nevertheless, the dissemination of the project through the standardization system, in physical meetings or using the digital tools of CEN, is also a very interesting source of visibility for the ECOBULK project.

The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE), as a European Standardization Body, is a partner in the ECOBULK project to provide support regarding the standardization tasks included in the project. In order to fulfil this commitment, the deliverable D8.6 "Report on the contribution to the standardization system " has been prepared to show the partners the steps to standardize the results of the project identified as potential new work item proposals, considering that Standardization has been used as a valuable input for the project. The deliverable D8.6 is part of Task 8.7 "Standardization activities". This final version of D8.6 summarizes the actions carried out and their results, regarding the interaction of the ECOBULK project consortium with the standardisation technical committees identified as relevant for the project, as well as the different standardisation results obtained such as published CWAs.

Abbreviations and acronyms

In this document the following abbreviations and acronyms are used:

CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC (CLC)	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
EN	European Standard
hEN	Harmonised European Standard
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
NMC	National Mirror Committee
NSB	National Standardization Body
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization; Spanish Standard
WG	Working Group
WI	Work Item

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1 Introduction

The general objective of Task 8.7 "Standardization activities" is to facilitate the acceptance and utilization by the market of the ECOBULK solutions, as well as to improve the development and the exploitation strategy of the ECOBULK project. Throughout the development of the ECOBULK project, several actions related to this have been implemented in Task 8.7 "Standardization". Deliverable D8.6 "Report on the contribution to standardization" summarizes the actions carried out and their results, regarding the interaction of the ECOBULK project consortium with the standardisation technical committees identified as relevant for the project, as well as the different standardization results obtained.

2 Action Plan for the contribution to standardization

2.1 General

As part of the standardization activities under Task 8.7, an Action Plan was defined in order to organize the different actions related to the standardisation activities within ECOBULK until the end of the project. This Action Plan was included in a document shared with all ECOBULK partners.

The conclusions of deliverable D8.5 "Report on the standardisation landscape and applicable standards" shown that several European and international technical committees exist, as well as standards and standards under development, related to ECOBULK project. These technical committees and their standards were seen as helpful for the development of the different ECOBULK work packages.

These conclusions also introduced several actions that may be performed in collaboration with the identified standardization technical committees, in order to interact with the standardization system for disseminating the project findings, as well as to contribute to ongoing standards under development or future standards.

The Action Plan links the most relevant identified standardization technical committees and the possible collaboration activities, also specifying possible dates, responsibilities and specific needs from ECOBULK partners.

Regarding the dissemination activities and based on the conclusions of Deliverable D8.5, the technical committees of this report have some relation to the ECOBULK project. Information on the most relevant Technical Committees (TCs) has been provided, listing standards references for the main topics identified for the fields related to the ECOBULK project.

- Plastics;
- Furniture;
- Automobiles;
- Wood, Wood-based panels and timber;
- Construction and construction products.
- Environmental Management;
- Circular Economy;

Table 1 shows the list of the main involved technical committees regarding these concepts and according to the conclusions of the deliverable D8.5, including the new technical committees identified posterior.

Table 1. Main Technical Committees identified in Deliverable D8.5

Subject	Technical Committee	Title
Plastics	CEN/TC 249	Plastics
	ISO/TC 61	Plastics
Wood, wood-based panels and timber	CEN/TC 112	Wood-based panels
	CEN/TC 38	Durability of Wood and Wood-based products
	CEN/TC 175	Round and sawn timber
	ISO/TC 89	Wood-based panels
	ISO/TC 218	Timber
	ISO/TC 165	Timber structures
Furniture	CEN/TC 207	Furniture
	CEN/TC 364	High chairs
	ISO/TC 136	Furniture
Automobiles	CEN/TC 248	Textiles and textile products
	ISO/TC 22	Road vehicles
	ISO/TC 38/SC 1	Textiles/ Tests for coloured textiles and colorants
	ISO/TC 38/WG 9	Textiles/ Nonwovens
	ISO/TC 45/SC 4	Rubber and rubber products/ products (other than hoses)
	ISO/TC 146/SC 6	Air quality/Indoor air
Construction and construction products	CEN/TC 350	Sustainability of construction works
	CEN/TC 127	Fire safety in buildings
	ISO/TC 92/SC 1	Fire safety/Fire initiation and growth
Environmental Management	CEN/SS S26	Environmental Management
Circular Economy	ISO/TC 323	Circular Economy
Chain of custody	ISO/PC 308	Chain of custody. General terminology and models
NOTE In this table is not included all the relevant SCs or WGs.		

3 Scope of this document

The contribution to the standardization of the results of the ECOBULK project is based on the interaction with the relevant Standardization Technical Committees; secondly the collaboration and communication with these TC; and finally, the standardization process.

This document summarizes the activities related to the standardization in the ECOBULK project, in order to give an overview of the path followed and to understand the context in which the subsequent actions have been developed.

The relevant Technical Committees identified in Deliverable D8.5 "Report on the contribution to the standardization" (see Table 1) have been considered. Moreover, three Technical Committees have been added: ISO/TC 323 "Circular Economy", ISO/PC 308 "Chain of custody", and CEN/TC 175 "Round and sawn timber".

ISO/TC 323 is a new Technical Committee, created (at the end of 2018) in the field of Circular Economy to standardize and develop, frameworks, guidance, support tools, and requirements for the implementation of activities of all involved organizations, to maximize the contribution to Sustainable Development.

ISO/PC 308 is a Project Committee, created in the field of Chain of Custody (CoC), including terminology, principles, requirements for and control systems used by supply chain actors with regards to the management of products in terms of their specified characteristics. The work is intended to be applicable to all products, whereas services are excluded.

In addition, other transversal documents to be considered for this project are the specific standards about the Circular Economy, namely, BS 8001: 2017 published by BSI and XP X30-901 published by AFNOR.

4 Definition of the Action Plan

The Action Plan comprises the actions included in Figure 1, and they are described in the following clauses.

4.1 General

The contribution of the ECOBULK project to standardization is influenced by external and internal factors: the level of development of the results obtained in the project, the interests of the partners and the feedback received from the TCs contacted.

The standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel of ECOBULK results towards the stakeholders represented in the standardization committees. In this regard, it seems necessary to define a strategy allowing the foreseen interaction with the standardization technical committees to be the most optima as possible. For it, several actions, and a schedule to implement them have been defined. Figure 1 shows Standardization activities for ECOBULK project.

Figure 1. Standardization activities for ECOBULK project

Note that the demand for interaction may be limited due to the time constraints of the ECOBULK project if made not possible to produce public deliverables that can be submitted to the relevant TCs as an innovative input to their standardization works.

In this regard, partners are advised that Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) on the ECOBULK outcomes should be carefully considered for further contribution to the standardization work, as standards organizations have implemented a Patent Policy that encourages the early disclosure and identification of Patents that may relate to standards under development. In doing so, greater efficiency in standards development is possible and potential patent rights problems can be avoided. Annex A gives guidance on the Patent Policy for CEN/CENELEC and for ISO/IEC/ITU.

4.2 Actions: step by step

Considering the conclusions obtained in Deliverable D8.5 and for the development of Deliverable D8.6, which includes the interaction with the standardization system and the future standardization proposals, it seems necessary to define a strategy allowing the foreseen interaction with the standardization technical committees to be the most effective and efficient as possible, through the definition of several actions included in Figure 2, and they are described in the following clauses:

Figure 2. Actions for the contribution to standardization of ECOBULK

4.2.1 Actions with regard to the first contact with the standardization technical committees

Document D8.5, issued in M8, provided an assessment of the standardization environment, including information regarding the state of the art in the standardization field and a brief evaluation of regulations related to standards and other constraints for the project. This list included in the first moment European and International committees.

Once the TCs involved in the ECOBULK project have been identified, it must be contacted. The main aim of this first contact is to raise awareness about ECOBULK among the relevant standardization committees and to ease subsequent contacts.

Knowing the importance of standardization as a tool to support European Union the legislation and policies, and that standards are substantial tools for the competitiveness of companies (especially SMEs, whose participation in the process of standardization and innovation is relevant for technological progress), it is important to know that the different categories of stakeholders at European and international level are involved in the technical committees and that they participate in standardization at all stages of the development of those standards where they may be involved. So, the standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel.

Feedback will be asked to gather any view, opinion or advise about the project and the standardization possibilities or needs. Note that these first contacts will be useful to determine the optimal path towards the initiation of a standardization process.

4.2.2 Monitoring and interaction with the standardization technical committees

Regarding the collaboration and communication to be carried out with the relevant CEN/CLC and ISO/IEC technical committees, the main factors that determine the more suitable interactions and relationship are:

- the impact/relevance of the standardization works of the technical committees; and
- the viability of initiating a standardization process within a technical committee.

In this phase, the ways of interaction of the project with the standardization committee's cover:

a) Monitoring of the activity of the relevant standardization technical committees.

This allows detecting the initiation of standardization works that can be relevant for ECOBULK and the progress of significant existing under-development standards. This is achievable through a periodical monitoring of the standardization activity resulting in updates of information, if necessary.

b) Later contact with the standardization committees to update the progress of ECOBULK.

Some of the activities carried out jointly with the TCs are, for example, to attend relevant technical committees' meetings, to deliver reports with summaries of updated of project, or joint events. On the one hand, this action contributes to further dissemination of the project and can guide the initiation of the standardization process. On the other hand, this later contact is mandatory towards the standardization committees directly covering (if it were the case) the subject that will be promoted by ECOBULK to undergo a standardization process.

c) Participation of one or more ECOBULK partners in the standardization technical committees.

Standardization is an open activity, and all interested parties may participate in the technical committees through the designation of their National Standardization Body. This option allows for a deeper follow-up of the activity of a standardization committee and is valuable if the standardization process is going to be initiated within the standardization committee. Annex B gives a list of National Standardization Bodies for CEN & CENELEC.

d) Establishment of a formal liaison of ECOBULK with the standardization committees.

Under the roll of "formal liaison", the consortium can participate in the TC works as an observer, without voting rights. This implies an economic cost, and it is recommended only when the work of the standardization committee is closely linked with the main goals of the project and a direct technical contribution from the project is expected. The figure of project liaison is recognized in CEN/CLC, but it doesn't exist in ISO/IEC.

At this point, it is worth recalling that, besides the cooperation between European and International TCs already explained in Deliverable D8.5, there are several mechanisms for cooperation between European Technical Committees: Informative relation, Contributively relation, Sub-contracting relation, Collaborative relation, and Integrated relation.

4.2.3 Standardization process

According to Task 8.7, the main objective of the standardization activities in ECOBULK is to facilitate the acceptance and utilization by the market of the developed solutions by transferring these results and findings to standards that have wide recognition in the market.

For getting this objective is fundamental the collaboration among all partners. First, the collaboration of the relevant partners the feasible results to go through a standardization process will be identified. After, different options to contribute to standardization shall be considered depending on the kind of the results and the standardization context (existence of closely related standards and reactions of the standardization committees):

a) Development of a new standard within a Standardization Workshop.

A standardization workshop is a group of entities with a common interest in developing a standard about a specific issue. It is the equivalent figure to the standardization committee, but the number of participants is typically smaller and the working procedures faster and more flexible. A standardization workshop is created when there is a need of developing a precise standard in an innovative field that is not covered by the existing standardization committees or when these committees are not interested in developing such standard (e.g., it does not fit in their work programme). If the subject is close to the field covered by a standardization committee it shall be informed and allow for the launching of the standardization workshop.

Considering that the standardization workshop option is interesting for ECOBULK mainly in the European environment, the standardization workshop will be named hereinafter as CEN Workshop. The standard produced by a CEN Workshop is called CEN Workshop Agreement (typically named as CWA). The nature and timeline for the development of CWAs is very suitable for the framework of the R&I projects.

b) Standardization within a Standardization Committee.

It may be interesting or needed that the results of ECOBULK to go through the standardization process are standardized within a standardization committee.

The possible scenarios are:

- ***Development of a new standard within a standardization committee.***

When there is a result of ECOBULK to be promoted to a standard in a field covered by a standardization committee and such committee decides to include this development in its work programme. The resulting standard would have the support of the standardization committee, but the work shall be adapted to the internal timeline of such standardization committee and could go beyond the timeframe of the project.

- ***Contribute to an on-going standard.***

As a consequence of the monitoring of the standardization landscape it may be found that the results of ECOBULK are covered by an on-going standard but that these results do not fit in the current draft of the standard. Gaps in standards may be found in both, standards that are being developed from a new initiative and standards already published that are going under a review process towards a new version.

- ***Request the modification of a standard that is not under development or review.***

The gap may be found also in published standards that are not under any work within the standardization committee. In this case, a fully justified modification request can be made to the standardization committee.

- ***Outline of a future standard.***

Only when there is not a clear view on a full roadmap for the contribution to standardization (like lack of agreement within the Consortium or lack of the expected results).

5 Execution of the plan

To carry out the plan, a series of actions must be carried out as described in clause 4. The actions and approach to be performed for the implementation of each of them are detailed next.

5.1 Actions regarding first contact with the standardization technical committees

Depending on the assessment by ECOBULK partners of the impact of the identified standardization committees on their tasks and the level of contribution that their results can represent for these committees, UNE has been working in coordination with partners of the consortium to define the first communication with selected technical committees according to Table 1.

For this, the following documents have been issued:

- List of secretaries and chairs of the identified technical committees and their contact data (see Annex C). In the first stage, communication will be focused on these committees.
- Content of the first communication mail (see Annex D), briefly explaining ECOBULK project and offering information exchange.

Moreover, this first step will ease future contacts if this process is launched within a standardization technical committee.

For the implementation of the actions described in 4.2.1 the relevance of the standardization committees identified in D8.5 shall be considered and contacted. Nevertheless, note that among the subjects identified in D8.5, ECOBULK project will innovate in matters related to its scope, i.e., among others, in the following concepts:

- new binder solutions for particle boards,
- increase in the percentage of recycled particle board used in production,
- develop new wood plastic composite (WPC) materials using 'waste' materials from diverse sources,
- incorporating salvaged plastics into internal car parts using composite materials,
- create a platform that can diagnose a range of possible options for any materials or products.

For the rest of the subjects identified in D8.5 not relevant innovation is expected in the project, their consideration is useful in terms of compatibility of the developments of ECOBULK.

UNE has contacted the Secretary of each selected standardization committee. The support of the Coordinator/Partners of ECOBULK have be needed to summarize the relevant progress and validate the information to disseminate avoiding any confidential content.

These first contacts were realized at M21 & M22. After that, and for lack of answers, we got back to contact them at M24.

The answer of technical committees has been sent from M22 until M27. Taking into account its answers, the Table 2 includes standardization committees proposed for subsequent interactions with the objectives described in 4.2.2.

Table 2. Identification of standardization committees to be contacted and monitored

Subject	Technical Body	Name	To be monitored
Plastics	CEN/TC 249	Plastics	YES
	ISO/TC 61	Plastics	YES
Wood, wood-based panels and timber	CEN/TC 112	Wood-based panels	YES
	CEN/TC 38	Durability of Wood and Wood-based products	YES
	CEN/TC 175	Round and sawn timber	YES
	ISO/TC 89	Wood-based panels	YES
	ISO/TC 218	Timber	YES
	ISO/TC 165	Timber structures	YES
Furniture	CEN/TC 207	Furniture	YES
	CEN/TC 364	High chairs	NO
	ISO/TC 136	Furniture	YES
Automobiles	CEN/TC 248	Textiles and textile products	NO
	ISO/TC 22	Road vehicles	YES
	ISO/TC 38/SC 1	Textiles/ Tests for coloured textiles and colorants	NO
	ISO/TC 38/WG 9	Textiles/ Nonwovens	NO
	ISO/TC 45/SC 4	Rubber and rubber products/ products (other than hoses)	YES
	ISO/TC 146/SC 6	Air quality/Indoor air	NO
Construction and construction products	CEN/TC 350	Sustainability of construction works	NO
	CEN/TC 127	Fire safety in buildings	NO
	ISO/TC 92/SC 1	Fire safety/Fire initiation and growth	NO
Environmental Management	CEN/SS S26	Environmental Management	NO
Circular Economy	ISO/TC 323	Circular Economy	NO
NOTE In this table is not included all the relevant SCs or WGs.			

5.2 Monitoring and interaction with the standardization technical committees

The implementation of the actions described in 4.2.2 starts with the monitoring of the work of the standardization committees included in Table 2. This surveillance will also include the analysis of European standardization workshops. The monitoring of the relevant standardization activity will be continuous during the timeframe of ECOBULK. The program of dates can be set:

- M21&22: first contact with the standardization committees.
- M30: proposals to be aligned with the needs of the standardization process described in 4.2.2.
- M36-M54: formal proposals according to the decision of the standardization process described in 4.2.3.

The standardization committees included in Table 2 will be updated with the relevant progress in ECOBULK. This will be done by updating the information provided in the subsequent interactions and, at the same time, keeping open the possibility of having a face-to-face interaction (e.g., attending a meeting of the standardization committee). For this case, the implication of the Coordinator and the partners is necessary to explain the technical details.

Mainly, the programming of these updates depends on the reactions to the subsequent contacts and on when the relevant outcomes of ECOBULK are delivered. Further interaction with the standardization committees (participation of members of ECOBULK in these committees and the consideration of a project liaison) is determined according to the outcomes of the described communications and the approach of the standardization process described in 4.2.3.

5.3 Standardization process

Regarding the identification of standardizable results, in the standardization landscape at the moment (a result of the interaction with the standardization committees and the monitoring of their standardization works) and the progress of the project, the most suitable roadmap among the options described in 4.2.3 will be selected and conducted.

With regards to the identification of all expected results, UNE contacted with the partners of ECOBULK project asking for their collaboration to get identify all results that will come out of the project. Since M27, UNE has contacted all partners, and the leaders of each WP have been completing the table with the results that could be used in the standardization activities. For more information about monitoring this activity, see Annex E.

The main aim of this table is to clearly identify all potential results in a simple format and that can become standard documents. There are different ways to exploit a result from the project either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing by:

- Using them in further research activities (outside the action)
- Developing, creating or marketing a product or process
- Creating and providing a service, or
- **Using them in standardization activities**

Those results that are identified as a key (in terms of market potential) could be subject to future standardization developments and therefore require to follow up assessment.

The feedback for this action was received in M29. A Technical document about the "Future Work Item Standardization System" (first version in M30 and updated in M36) has been prepared, as support for Deliverable D8.6. This Technical report offered an opportunity to identify the possibility of linking the results to the technical standardization committees (TC) involved in the project.

Based both on the information provided by the evaluation of the relevant TC and the ECOBULK results at that time that could be standardized, it was necessary to make an assessment that would allow ECOBULK members to decide regarding further steps in the standardization process and the election of the most suitable roadmap among the options described in 4.2.3.

It should be noted that the standardization process is considered very valuable for the market acceptance of ECOBULK results and for the impact of this project beyond the funding period. The decisions taken, actions carried out, as well as the results obtained have been recorded in this D8.6.

5.4 Summary of the actions and schedule

Taking into account all the information previously presented, a strategy implementation schedule was made in order to develop deliverable D8.6. The schedule is included in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of the actions in the strategy for the development D8.6

Nº	Action	Responsible	Month
1	Content of the first email	UNE (content approved by the coordinator and leader WP8)	M20 &M21
2	First contacts with the standardization committees in Table 1	UNE	M21 &M22
3	Follow-up of the first answer of TC	UNE	Until M27
4	Monitoring and subsequent interactions with the standardization committees in Table 2	UNE	Continuous
5	Updates on the standardization landscape	UNE	Continuous
6	Content of email to get the identification of all expected results to be used in standardization activities	UNE (content approved by leader WP8)	M27
7	Identification of all expected results to be used in standardization activities	All leader of WP	Until M29
8	Provision of updated report/information to the standardization committees identified in Table 2	UNE (content provided by the Coordinator)	M30, M36, M48
9			Whenever it is demanded
10	Face to face interaction with the relevant standardization committees	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	When relevant
11	Participation in a TC: The secretary of CEN/TC 38 invited to participate in the next plenary meeting (on the 14 of Nov)	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	M29 (to be decided)
12	Presentation of the project in TCs meeting	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	When relevant
13	Discussion about the options of standardization session if it was necessary	UNE	M30
14	Standardization process (election of the most suitable roadmap)	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	M30-M54

5.5 Actions

In each of the work packages of the project, they have been identified, based on technical criteria, (structure similar to European standards, technical content, the scope of the document, possible interest for the entire sector) those deliverables already published within the consortium (or that they will be published within the required timeframe) on which it is necessary to decide if they are submitted to the European or International standardization system as potential Work Items.

The deliverables that were identified by UNE and by the members of the consortium as possible normative documents and that have not been accepted by the standardization committees either due to lack of interest or because their technical content is not within their fields of activity (for further information, see Annex F "Roadmap for the standardization process"), they could be submitted to a later study, if applicable.

On the other hand, the ECOBULK consortium was informed on the possibility to develop standardization documents as a helpful way to disseminate the project findings and increase its impact, to facilitate the acceptance and utilization by the market of the developed solutions, and to support the implementation of the recovery of composite in a model of economy circular. This possibility was well received and some ECOBULK results (deliverables) were identified as "standardizable", as shown in Annex E.

6 Development of CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA)

6.1 Decision to develop standardisation documents

During the Review meeting of ECOBULK project on M36, the consortium agreed to development of standardization documents. Once agreed, it was needed to define the type of document to be developed. Since EN or ISO standards, technical specifications or technical reports may need several years until publication, it was considered the CEN workshop agreement (CWA) as the most feasible type of document to be developed during the ECOBULK timeframe.

A CWA is an agreement developed and approved in a CEN Workshop, which is a technical body open to the direct participation of anyone with an interest in the development of the agreement. There is no geographical limit on participation. The development of a CWA is fast and flexible, on average 12-18 months.

Regarding the Deliverables that were identified as "standardizable" (see Annex E.3), the following list of "CWA candidates" was proposed:

Table 4. List of standardizable deliverables "CWA candidates"

ECOBULK standardizable results identified by partners		
Partner	Standardization gap detected	Deliverable or task to be converted
ITENE	Report on Design Circular Framework Setting	Deliverable D2.4
BELLVER	Dismantling methods and protocols	Deliverable D5.2

The development of the CWA as normative documents based on these "CWA candidates" is carried out taking into account, among others, the **reference documents** which give guidelines on how to draft standards: CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreements ([CEN GUIDE 29](#)) and CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations ([Part 3](#)).

6.2 CEN Workshop creation

According to the CEN rules, the creation of a CEN Workshop is needed to develop CWAs. This implies the elaboration of a Project Plan¹⁾, a Self-Assessment²⁾, and the celebration of a Kick-off meeting.

The creation of the CEN Workshop ECOBULK (CEN/WS 113) on "Framework linking dismantled parts with new design components for the automotive industry in a circular economy model" was announced on the CEN website on 2020-11-24, allowing any interested organization to join, and the Kick-off Meeting was celebrated online on 2021-01-12 with the participation of different European organizations, including several ECOBULK partners.

During this event it was presented the CEN Workshop's Work programme, which corresponded to two CWAs:

- **CWA XXXX: "Design Circular Framework Setting. Composite recovery design solutions in the automotive industry"**, identifies and establishes design solutions and strategies to enhance the vehicle parts durability, and at the same time facilitate their maintenance and repair, dismantling and disassembly, reusing and remanufacturing, as well as the material recovery.
- **CWA YYYY: "Dismantling methods and protocols in a Circular Economy Framework. Composite recovery in the automotive industry"**, specifies strategies, technologies and protocols for collection and material recovery (plastics, foam, glass, fibres from vehicle parts) for (re-) manufacturing, in addition to parts that are already being recycled.

1) The CEN Workshop Project Plan is the document that justifies the creation of the CEN Workshop (explaining the market environment and the motivation) and explains its scope and objectives. It also provides information on the participants and the work programme, with a defined calendar.

2) The Self-Assessment is a document that allows to check if a CWA included in the CEN Workshop work programme conflicts with any other standard or technical committee scope or deals with safety or management systems. In these cases, the development of CWAs maybe restricted.

Figure 3. CEN Workshop ECOBULK (CEN/WS 113) Kick-off meeting

6.3 CWA drafting and publication

The elaboration of the CWA followed several stages, through a consensus-based process to ensure openness, transparency and participation, and involved all CEN Workshop ECOBULK (CEN/WS 113) participants in a first phase, and all other interested European organizations in a second phase.

After the Kick-off meeting, the partners responsible for the CWAs drafting started the work to adapt some of the ECOBULK results into the programmed CWAs according to the European standardization common practice and rules.

At the end of January, a first preliminary version of the CWAs was circulated to the workshop members, which participated performing several editorial and technical comments, and that were duly addressed, replied and most of them included in the draft CWAs. The final documents were circulated again to the CEN Workshop ECOBULK (CEN/WS 113) for final approval and to the relevant CEN Technical Committees for information, being the agreement achieved on 2021-04-23.

After this, the draft CWAs were sent to CEN in order to make them available in the CEN website for information of any interested European organisation, allowing their consultation and commenting during a 30-day period. During this period no comments were received. Finally, both CWAs were published by CEN on 2021-10-06, with the following references:

- **CWA 17806:2021**- Design Circular Framework Setting. Composite recovery design solutions in the automotive industry
- **CWA 17807:2021**- Dismantling methods and protocols in a Circular Economy Framework. Composite recovery in the automotive industry

Both CWA are downloadable for free through the [CWA 17806 & CWA 17807-download-area](#). First pages of the CWAs can be found in Annex G.

Figure 4. ECOBULK CWAs covers

7 Conclusion

Standardization facilitates the recognition, acceptance, use and future exploitation of project solutions. For this reason, it is considered a highly valued activity as part of research and innovation projects, acting as an ally to disseminate the project results to the industry, society and public administrations.

Standardization also enables interoperability and compatibility of innovative solutions with existing products, services or processes, and facilitates trade by reducing technical barriers. Standards generate trust since they ensure that a product, service or system complies with expectations and requirements of the market or public procurement.

In the case of the ECOBULK project, and with respect to the contribution to standardization, the following relevant results have been obtained:

- On one hand, the consortium has been able to develop two standardization proposals based on the experience of some partners using standards in their daily work and in the developments within ECOBULK. These proposals could lead in the future to the revision of existing standards in order to improve them according to new and innovative solutions.
- On the other hand, the main contribution to the standardization of ECOBULK is the publication of the two CWA. Thanks to these documents, the impact and visibility of the ECOBULK project and its partners will be increased, boosting its knowledge by the market. The publication of these CWA contributes to fulfilling objective 8 of the "Grant Agreement of ECOBULK (Number 730456)".

Objective 8. Address the barriers to facilitate the transition towards circular economy and assess side-effects and risks of the products *[Aligned with the WP8]*

Current and future gaps that could act as barriers to the development of a circular model will be evaluated. Existing bottlenecks on transition from linear to circular approach in value and supply chains will be identified as well as existing and in the pipeline solutions to overcome them. Policy recommendations to foster the near-zero waste economy will be proposed. Examples include: lack of internalisation of externalities through policy, lack of resource pricing (cost recovery and pricing for the recovered materials); lack of skills and investment in circular product design and production; lack of enablers to improve cross-cycle and cross-sector performance due inter alia to non-alignment of power and incentives for transformation between actors within and across value chains; lack of consumer and business acceptance regarding consumer-as-user. A comprehensive risk register will be developed early in the project lifetime and appropriate mitigation strategies will be defined by the consortium members.

KPIs: By M24, a first reviewing of the barriers to overcome for the implementation of the EcoBulk's circular approach will be developed and by M39, organisations, countries and EU specific recommendations will be provided to support transition.

Figure 5. Objective 8 of the "Grant Agreement of ECOBULK (Number 730456)"

Annex A – Patent policy

A.1 Standardization and intellectual property rights (IPR) for CEN/CENELEC

CEN and CENELEC have had intellectual property rights (IPR) policy for many years under the provision of the CEN-CENELEC Guide 8 "Standardization and intellectual property rights (IPR)". The purpose of these common guidelines is to provide in simple words practical guidance to the participants in their technical bodies in case patent or other intellectual property rights matters arise.

For the sake of clarity, this document refers to "patents", as most - but not all - IPR issues that CEN and CENELEC technical bodies must deal with concern patent rights. However, the same implementation principles shall apply to other statutory intellectual property rights based on inventions that may arise, such as utility models or registered semiconductor topographies (see Clause 2, Terms and definitions).

Considering that technical experts are not normally familiar with the complex issue of patent law, the Common Patent Policy for ISO/IEC/ITU endorsed by CEN and CENELEC (hereafter referred to as the "Patent Policy") was drafted in its operative part as a checklist covering the three different cases which may arise if a deliverable requires licences for patents to be practiced or implemented, fully or partly.

These Guidelines for Implementation of the Common Policy on Patents for CEN and CENELEC (hereafter referred to as the "Guidelines") are intended to complement, clarify and facilitate the implementation of the Patent Policy, a copy of which can be found in Guide 8, Annex 1 and also on the websites of both organisations.

The CEN and CENELEC Patent Policy request stakeholders participating in technical Committees, and patent holders, to proceed to early disclosures and identification of patents that may be considered, at the best of their knowledge, to be essential for the future use of the deliverables under development. In doing so, greater efficiency in standards development is possible and potential patent rights problems can be avoided.

CEN and CENELEC are not involved in evaluating patent relevance or essentiality about deliverables, nor to interfere with licensing negotiations, or engage in settling disputes on patents. This is left to the parties concerned. For further information see [CEN-CENELEC Guide 8](#).

A.2 Common Patent Policy for ISO/IEC/ITU

In the light of the need to balance the competing interests of standard-essential patent (SEP) holders and standards implementers and aiming to develop standards that reflect the best available technical solutions, SDOs have established rules (usually referred to as IPR policies or patent policies) governing the inclusion of patents in standards. These IPR policies generally require that patent holders disclose their SEPs during a standard's development and that they make commitments to licensing such SEPs to all standards implementers under reasonable and non-discriminatory conditions.

In a typical standardization process, it is the participants that drive a standard's development by proposing the inclusion of what they deem to be the most appropriate methodologies, technologies or technical solutions. The development of such methodologies, technologies or technical solutions is often a complex, costly endeavour demanding investments in R&D that can span several years. Yet, for a variety of reasons, many companies volunteer their patented innovations for inclusion in standards.

Standards can incorporate literally thousands of patents, and the associated difficulties have been compounded by the fact that the development of standards sometimes anticipates the progression of technology rather than following it.

A standard-essential patent (SEP) is one that is indispensable to the implementation of a standard. A patent is considered standard-essential if the text of a standard is drafted in such a way that it becomes impossible to implement the specifications of the standard without using the technology protected by the patent. While there may be (and usually are) many patent-protected innovations able to add value to standards-based products, these are not necessarily essential as per the above definition.

Most standards bodies have developed IPR policies that allow for companies' patent-protected innovations to be reflected in standards, provided that such intellectual property is made available to all standards implementers under royalty-free or reasonable and non-discriminatory terms and conditions.

The inclusion of patented technology in standards is very common today. One explanation for this is that the inclusion of patented technology adds to standards' ability to improve performance, cost-effectiveness, connectivity or interoperability. Another is that patents have come to cover a larger portion of our society's overall knowledge base. A further, complementary explanation for the increase in SEPs is that they serve the strategic interests of market players, which see a considerable benefit to having their patented technologies selected as part of a standard.

Companies owning SEPs benefit from new revenue-generating opportunities in that every implementer of a standard is by definition infringing the associated SEPs unless they acquire licenses to these SEPs from their owners. SEP owners possess strong bargaining positions in cross-licensing deals that grant them access to other patents. Companies also benefit from contributing patented technology to a standard because the widespread adoption of that standard might signify a change in market direction that suits a SEP owner's strengths and expertise or existing products, platforms and clients, thereby giving them a competitive advantage by their having less need than their competitors to remodel their product offerings.

Although the patent and standardization systems both aim to support and incentivize innovation and technological progress, the intersection of these two mechanisms may give rise to various tensions and conflicts. The standardization system is based on the assumption of commonalities, creating an even playing field for competition by granting stakeholders equal access to innovative solutions.

Conversely, the patent system is based on the award of temporary monopolies borne of IPR holders' ability to exclude others from implementing protected technologies. The contrasting principles of the inclusivity of standards and exclusivity of IPR do not meet without complexity. For further information see [ISO/IEC/ITU Common Patent Policy](#).

Annex B – List of National Standards Bodies (NSB)

B.1 CEN members

Acronym	Country	Organization	Website
ASI	Austria	Austrian Standards International - Standardization and Innovation	www.austrian-standards.at
NBN	Belgium	Bureau de Normalisation/Bureau voor Normalisatie	www.nbn.be
BDS	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Institute for Standardization	www.bds-bg.org
HZN	Croatia	Croatian Standards Institute	www.hzn.hr
CYS	Cyprus	Cyprus Organization for Standardisation	www.cys.org.cy
UNMZ	Czech Republic	Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing	www.unmz.cz
DS	Denmark	Dansk Standard	www.ds.dk
EVS	Estonia	Estonian Centre for Standardisation	www.evs.ee
SFS	Finland	Suomen Standardisoimisliitto r.y.	www.sfs.fi
AFNOR	France	Association Française de Normalisation	www.afnor.org
DIN	Germany	Deutsches Institut für Normung	www.din.de
NQIS/ELOT	Greece	National Quality Infrastructure System	www.elot.gr
MSZT	Hungary	Hungarian Standards Institution	www.mszt.hu
IST	Iceland	Icelandic Standards	www.stadlar.is
NSAI	Ireland	National Standards Authority of Ireland	www.nsai.ie
UNI	Italy	Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione	www.uni.com
LVS	Latvia	Latvian Standard Ltd.	www.lvs.lv
LST	Lithuania	Lithuanian Standards Board	www.lsd.lt
ILNAS	Luxembourg	Organisme Luxembourgeois de Normalisation	www.portail-qualite.lu
MCCAA	Malta	The Malta Competition and Consumer Affairs Authority	https://mccaa.org.mt
NEN	Netherlands	Nederlands Normalisatie-instituut	www.nen.nl
SN	Norway	Standards Norway	www.standard.no/
PKN	Poland	Polish Committee for Standardization	www.pkn.pl
IPQ	Portugal	Instituto Português da Qualidade	www.ipq.pt
ISRSM	Republic of North Macedonia	Standardization Institute of the Republic of North Macedonia	www.isrm.gov.mk

Acronym	Country	Organization	Website
ASRO	Romania	Romanian Standards Association	www.asro.ro
ISS	Serbia	Institute for Standardization of Serbia	www.iss.rs
UNMS SR	Slovakia	Slovak Office of Standards Metrology and Testing	www.unms.sk
SIST	Slovenia	Slovenian Institute for Standardization	www.sist.si
UNE	Spain	Asociación Española de Normalización	www.une.org
SIS	Sweden	Swedish Institute for Standards - SIS	www.sis.se
SNV	Switzerland	Schweizerische Normen-Vereinigung	www.snv.ch
TSE	Turkey	Turkish Standards Institution	www.tse.org.tr
BSI	United Kingdom	British Standards Institution	www.bsigroup.com

B.2 CENELEC members

Acronym	Country	Description	Website
AFNOR-FrSS-UTE	France	AFNOR-French Standardization System-UTE	www.afnor.org
ASRO	Romania	Romanian Standards Association	www.asro.ro
BDS	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Institute for Standardization	www.bds-bg.org
BSI	United Kingdom	British Standards Institution	www.bsigroup.com
CEB-BEC	Belgium	Comité Electrotechnique Belge/Belgisch Elektrotechnisch Comité	www.ceb-bec.be
CEI	Italy	Comitato Elettrotecnico Italiano	www.ceinorme.it
CYS	Cyprus	Cyprus Organization for Standardisation	www.cys.org.cy
DKE	Germany	German Commission for Electrical, Electronic and Information Technologies of DIN and VDE	www.dke.de
DS	Denmark	Dansk Standard	www.ds.dk
Electrosuisse	Switzerland	Association for Electrical Engineering, Power and Information Technologies	www.electrosuisse.ch
EVS	Estonia	Estonian Centre for Standardisation	www.evs.ee
HZN	Croatia	Croatian Standards Institute	www.hzn.hr
ILNAS	Luxembourg	Organisme Luxembourgeois de Normalisation	www.portail-qualite.lu
IPQ	Portugal	Instituto Português da Qualidade	www.ipq.pt

Acronym	Country	Description	Website
ISRSM	Republic of North Macedonia	Standardization Institute of the Republic of North Macedonia	www.isrm.gov.mk
ISS	Serbia	Institute for Standardization of Serbia	www.iss.rs
IST	Iceland	Icelandic Standards	www.stadlar.is
LST	Lithuania	Lithuanian Standards Board	www.lsd.lt
LVS	Latvia	Latvian Standard Ltd.	www.lvs.lv
MCCAA	Malta	The Malta Competition and Consumer Affairs Authority	https://mccaa.org.mt
MSZT	Hungary	Hungarian Standards Institution	www.mszt.hu
NEC	Netherlands	Nederlands Electrotechnisch Comité	www.nen.nl
NEK	Norway	Norsk Elektroteknisk Komite	www.nek.no
NQIS/ELOT	Greece	National Quality Infrastructure System	www.elot.gr
NSAI	Ireland	National Standards Authority of Ireland	www.nsai.ie
OVE	Austria	Austrian Electrotechnical Association	www.ove.at
PKN	Poland	Polish Committee for Standardization	www.pkn.pl
SEK	Sweden	Svensk Elstandard	www.elstandard.se
SESKO	Finland	Finnish Electrotechnical Standards Association	www.sesko.fi
SIST	Slovenia	Slovenian Institute for Standardization	www.sist.si
TSE	Turkey	Turkish Standards Institution	www.tse.org.tr
UNE	Spain	Asociación Española de Normalización	www.une.org
UNMS SR	Slovakia	Slovak Office of Standards Metrology and Testing	www.unms.sk
UNMZ	Czech Republic	Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing	www.unmz.cz

Annex C – List of secretaries and chairs of the identified technical committees

Reference	Technical body title	Technical Secretary	Secretary	Chairperson
CEN/SS S26	Environmental Management	CCMC	CCMC PM	Mrs A. Nam
CEN/TC 38	Durability of Wood and Wood-based products	AFNOR	Mr A. Gaudron	Ms M. Kutnik
CEN/TC 112	Wood-based panels	DIN	Mr B. Trepkau	Dipl.-Ing. S. Tobisch
CEN/TC 112/WG 11	Particleboards and fibreboards	DIN	Mr B. Trepkau	Mr K. Wijnendaele
CEN/TC 112/WG 2	Plywood	AFNOR	Ms A. Le Ferrec	
CEN/TC 112/WG 4	Test methods	DIN	Mr B. Trepkau	
CEN/TC 112/WG 5	Regulated dangerous substances	DIN	Mr B. Trepkau	
CEN/TC 112/WG 7	Semi-finished and finished products	AFNOR	Ms A. Le Ferrec	Mr C. Héleu
CEN/TC 112/WG 9	Solid Wood panels	ASI	Mrs A. Gapp	
CEN/TC 127	Fire safety in buildings	BSI	Mr D. Hyde	Dr D. Smith
CEN/TC 175	Round and Sawn timber	AFNOR	Mr F. Henry	Mr P. Pangault
CEN/TC 175/ WG 3	Sawn timber	To be assigned		
CEN/TC 207	Furniture	UNI	Mr F. Tacca	Mr M. Fossi
CEN/TC 207/ WG 2	Requirements for children's and nursery furniture	AFNOR	Mr A. Gaudron	Mme C. Follin-Arbelet
CEN/TC 207/ WG 3	Office furniture	AFNOR	Mr A. Gaudron	Mr J-P. Schnell
CEN/TC 207/ WG 5	Requirements for non-domestic furniture	BSI	Mr P. Reynolds	
CEN/TC 207/ WG 7	Requirements and test methods for furniture surfaces	DIN	Mr U. Deubel	Dr R. Emmler
CEN/TC 207/ WG 9	Test methods	BSI	Mr P. Reynolds	
CEN/TC 248	Textiles and textile products	BSI	Ms J. Duncan	Dr T. Sagar
CEN/TC 249	Plastics	NBM	Mr H. Janssens	Mr H. Omloo

Reference	Technical body title	Technical Secretary	Secretary	Chairperson
CEN/TC 249/ WG 11	Plastics recycling	DIN	Mrs S. Bierwirth	Mr J. Lühr
CEN/TC 249/ WG 13	Wood Plastics Composites (WPC)	DIN	Mrs L. Dehne	Mr R. Lietzmann
CEN/TC 249/ WG 15	Fibre-reinforced composites	SN	Mr K. Aune	Dr J. Taby
CEN/TC 249/ WG 17	Biopolymers	UNI	Mr G. Moroni	Mr F. Degli Innocenti
CEN/TC 249/ WG 19	Light exposure	AFNOR	M. Y. Archambeau	Mr X. Duteurtre
CEN/TC 350	Sustainability of construction works	AFNOR	Mme K. Dari	Mr A. Ilomaki
CEN/TC 364	High chairs	UNI	Mr P. Santato	Mr M. Bonazzi
ISO/TC 136	Furniture	UNI	Mr Fabrizio Tacca	Mr Marco Fossi
ISO/TC 136/ WG 3	Storage units - Test methods for determination of strength and durability	UNI	Mr Fabrizio Tacca	Mr Marco Fossi
ISO/TC 146/ SC 6	Air quality/Indoor air	DIN	Mrs Dr Elisabeth Hösen-Seul	Mr Shin-ichi Tanabe
ISO/TC 165	Timber structures	SCC	Mr Paul Jaehrlich	Mr Ying Chui
ISO/TC 218	Timber	DSTU	Mr Oleh Miroshnyk	Mr Oleksii Tsytsyliano
ISO/TC 22	Road vehicles	AFNOR	Mme Valérie Maupin	M Marc Corona
ISO/TC 323	Circular Economy	AFNOR	M Olivier Cartigny	Mrs Catherine Chevauche
ISO/PC 308	Circular Economy	NEN	Mr R. Busink	Mrs Juliane Eykelhoff
ISO/TC 38/ SC 1	Textiles/Tests for coloured textiles and colorants	BSI	Mr Brian Woolley	Dr Jinping GUAN
ISO/TC 38/ WG 9	Textiles/Nonwovens	SAC	Mr Yong Xu	Mr Hisashi Tazawa
ISO/TC 45/ SC 4	Rubber and rubber products/products (other than hoses)	DSM	Mrs Ainal Fatiha Mohd Noor	Dr Amir Hashim Md Yatim
ISO/TC 61	Plastics	SAC	Mr Jiandong Wang	Dr Hubert Simon
ISO/TC 61/ SC 11	Products	JISC	Mr Shinji Date	Dr Kazukiyo Nagai
ISO/TC 61/ SC 11/WG 11	Wood-plastic composites	JISC	Mr Shinji Date	Dr Kazukiyo Nagai
ISO/TC 61/ SC 13/WG 2	Laminates and moulding compounds	JISC	Mr Ryo Saito	Dr Masaki Hojo

Reference	Technical body title	Technical Secretary	Secretary	Chairperson
ISO/TC 89	Wood-based panels	DIN	Mr Dipl.-Holzwirt Bernd Trepkau	Mr Dipl.-Ing Harald Schwab
ISO/TC 89/ SC 1	Fibre boards	SA	Ms Kylie Schumacher	Mr Prof. Dr. rer. nat Steffen Tobisch
ISO/TC 89/ SC 2	Particle boards	SA	Ms Kylie Schumacher	Mr Prof. Dr. rer. nat Steffen Tobisch
ISO/TC 89/ SC 3	Plywood	AFNOR	Mlle Ambre Le Ferrec	Mr Gaetano Castro
ISO/TC 89/ WG 5	Test methods	DIN	Mr Dipl.-Holzwirt Bernd Trepkau	Mr Dipl.-Ing Harald Schwab
ISO/TC 92/ SC 1	Fire safety/Fire initiation and growth	BSI	Mr Bernd Borchert	Mrs Christine Lukas

Annex D – Communication texts with TC

D.1 First communication text

About this matter, UNE has collaborated with the partners and finally, UNE sent this first communication to the selected Technical Committees according to the list of most relevant standardization TCs included in Table 1. The content of this first communication included a summary ECOBULK project, external link to the ECOBULK website, and offered information exchange.

An example of this communication is as follow:

Horizon 2020- ECOBULK Project - Standardization Activities. CEN/TC 249 "Plastics"

 Isabel Linares Nicolas
Para 'nhj@telenet.be'
CC 'JUribe@iswa.org'

ju. 28/03/2019 17:04

 Respondió a este mensaje el 08/06/2020 10:47.

Dear Mr H. Janssens,

First, allow me I introduce myself; my name is Isabel LINARES and work for UNE (Spanish Standardization Body). I'm addressing you on behalf of the ECOBULK project (H2020 frame), in which UNE is a partner in charge of tasks related to standardization, including proposals for future European standards. The main objective of the Standardization activities is to facilitate the acceptance and utilization by the market of the developed solutions.

The ECOBULK project (*Circular Process for Eco-Designed Bulky Products and Internal Car Parts*) and it will contribute to "closing the loop" of composite products in the automotive, furniture and building sectors by promoting greater re-use, upgrade, refurbishment and recycle of products, parts, and materials. The ECOBULK project will be based on identifying and promoting commonalities in processes, technologies, products and services ensuring replicability and transferability to other industrial sectors. The application of the circular economy model in the three selected sectors is justified by the high numbers of synergies, in terms of the design, materials, manufacturing technology and business models. For further information, see <https://ecobulk.eu/>.

One of the aims of this contact is to raise awareness on the project to this TC and gather feedback on any suggestions, questions or comments related to it at this point. When they become available, it is intended that the content and results of this project be considered by the TC as possibly useful inputs for contributing to future or ongoing standardization works or for identifying standardization needs within to the TC work program. If you need further information at this point or would like to talk to others involved in the project, please contact me.

Please, inform to involved structure too:

- CEN/TC 249/WG 11 "Plastics recycling". Secretary: Mrs S. Bierwirth
- CEN/TC 249/WG 13 "Wood Plastics Composites (WPC)". Secretary: Mrs L. Dehne
- CEN/TC 249/WG 15 "Fibre-reinforced composites". Secretary: Mr K. Aune
- CEN/TC 249/WG 17 "Biopolymers". Secretary: Mr G. Moroni
- CEN/TC 249/WG 19 "Light exposure". Secretary: M. Y. Archambeau

We would appreciate if you could provide this **feedback before May 15th**.

Thank you very much in advance.

Isabel LINARES
Pressure equipment, installations & NDT Program Manager
UNE- Asociación Española de Normalización
Tel. +34 914 326 001
ilinares@une.org

D.2 Other communications

The first contact aims to inform the relevant standardization committees, where different categories of stakeholders at the European/international level are participating, and raise awareness about the ECOBULK project, facilitating subsequent contacts.

After that, the subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees has been continuous and updated until M54 according to the last information about standardization in their respective scope.

Annex E – Identification of expected results

E.1 First email for data collection in the ECOBULK consortium

Concerning the identification of all expected results, UNE has collaborated with the partners of ECOBULK project asking for their collaboration. The content of this communication included a brief explanation to obtain the aim and to fill in a table for WP8, and the table itself. A copy of this communication is as follow:

ECOBULK project: Standardization activities. "Identification of all expected results"

Isabel Linares Nicolas
Para [Dominik Jasinski](#); [juergen.pfitzer@tecnaro.de](#); [michael.schweizer@tecnaro.de](#); [Abdullahi Ahmed](#); [Ajith Kularathna Aluvihare Gedara](#); [Alessio Gualtieri](#); [Alexandre Ventura](#); [Ana ORTEGA DE LUIS](#); [Andreas Kleinschmit](#); [Aneta Pawlik](#); [Anna Furberg](#); [Anne Gallou](#); y **76 usuarios más** vi. 27/09/2019 12:58

Mensaje reenviado el 12/03/2020 12:03.

RESULTS TABLE FOR WP8-ECOBULK.docx
20 KB

Dear partners,

I am writing to request your collaboration with regard to the "Identification of all expected results" coming from WP.

We would like all WP leaders to complete the following "table" (see the attached document: "RESULTS TABLE FOR WP8"). When it is completed will serve as a summary reference for the results of the project.

RESULTS TABLE FOR WP8-ECOBULK.docx

The aim of this table is to clearly identify ALL RESULTS that will come out of the project in a simple format. Please remember that there are different ways to exploit a result from the project either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing by:

- Using them **in further research activities** (outside the action)
- Developing, creating or marketing **a product or process**
- Creating and providing **a service**, or
- **Using them in standardization activities**

Those results that are identified as a key (in terms of market potential) and the same of them could be subject to future standardization developments and therefore require to follow up assessment. Note that the table has to include all the results of ECOBULK but highlighting those results that can become CWA. The rapid development opportunities offered by a CWA are considered to be particularly attractive for European research projects (e.g., H2020) which have to deliver within the duration of their project lifetime. The role of the leader or partner for each CWA is fundamental to reach success.

As a summary, we should be getting at least 1 CWA. It would be perfect if we get to elaborate three CWAs, one for the automobile sector, other for the plastic sector and the other for furniture or wood. Finally, all will depend on the kinds of the results and the available time to deliver the CWA within the timeframe of the project.

As you know, OAKDENE HOLLINS (Ms. Olivia Bertham) is leading WP8, but the knowledge needs to come from the relevant partners, and UNE needs your collaboration in order to follow up of standardization activities. Therefore, we request that all partners fill out the table with their own results, if possible **before 2019-11-29**.

We look forward to receiving your inputs for the results table and, as always, your comments will be welcome.

Best regards,

Isabel LINARES
UNE- Asociación Española de Normalización
Tel. +34 914 326 001
ilinares@une.org

The attached document is exposed in the following page:

RESULTS TABLE FOR WPS

Please use the table to identify summary details of all expected results. In particular please try to identify those results that partners feel to be an exploitable result

N ^o	Result – brief description	WP	Lead Partner	Other partners	Is there an exploitable result? Y/N	Possible exploitation route	A/B/C/D/E/O See NOTE	Deliverable number	Dissemination level	Is there a short paper of Deliverable? Y/N	Issue a short paper Due date	Comments
1	Sustainable procurement, retail and product tracking and labelling system.	WP 6	ITENE	¿?¿	Y?	Add-on module to be sold to existing customers. It will include the analysis of the current situation, the future vision, the identification of the risks and barriers...	¿¿?	D6.2	Public	N?	xx-xx-xxxx	Example only

NOTE: Please, indicate the nature of activity foreseen for this result by the partners involved using the following claim keys:

- (A) Make result and sell it;
- (B) Use result internally to make a new result to be sold;
- (C) Use result for further research;
- (D) License result to a 3rd party;
- (E) Provide services pertaining to result (training, consultancy,);
- (O) Other exploitation route not already listed.

Please remember the instructions from the European Commission: "Each beneficiary must:

- up to four years after the project completion, take measures aiming to ensure "exploitation" of its results, either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing by:
- Using them **in further research activities** (outside the action)
- Developing, creating or marketing **a product or process**
- Creating and providing **a service**, or
- **Using them in standardization activities"**

The aim of the exposed table is to clearly identify ALL RESULTS that will come out of the project in a simple format. It should be noted that there are different ways to exploit a result from the project either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing by:

- Using them **in further research activities** (outside the action)
- Developing, creating or marketing **a product or process**
- Creating and providing a service, or
- **Using them in standardization activities**

Those results that are identified as a key (in terms of market potential) and the same of them could be subject to future standardization developments and therefore require to follow up assessment. Note that the table has to include all the results of ECOBULK but highlighting those results that can become CWA. The rapid development opportunities offered by a CWA are considered to be particularly attractive for European research projects (e.g., H2020) which have to deliver within the duration of their project lifetime. The role of the leader or partner for each CWA is fundamental to reach success.

E.2 Table for WP8 of all expected results

The table for WP6 has been sent to all WP leaders. The goal was to complete it to identify all the expected and exploitable results. We request collaboration from all partners to use the table of WP8 to identify summary details of all expected results, i.e. the results to be exploitable (KER).

An example has been included in the table.

RESULTS TABLE FOR WP8

Please use the table to identify summary details of all expected results. In particular please try to identify those results that partners feel to be an exploitable result

No	Result - brief description	WP	Lead Partner	Other partners	Is there an exploitable result?	Possible exploitation route	A/B/C/D/E/O	Deliverable number	Dissemination level	Is there a short paper of Deliverable?	Issue a short paper	Comments
					Y/N		See NOTE			Y/N	Due date	
1	Sustainable procurement, retail and product tracking and labelling system.	WP6	ITENE	???	Y?	Add-on module to be sold to existing customers. It will include the analysis of the current situation, the future vision, the identification of the risks and barriers...	???	D6.2	Public	N?	xx-xx-xxxx	Example only

NOTE: Please, indicate the nature of activity foreseen for this result by the partners involved using the following claim keys:
(A) Make result and sell it;
(B) Use result internally to make a new result to be sold;
(C) Use result for further research;
(D) License result to a 3rd party;
(E) Provide services pertaining to result (training, consultancy.);
(O) Other exploitation route not already listed.

Please remember the instructions from the European Commission: "Each beneficiary must:
 - up to four years after the project completion, take measures aiming to ensure "exploitation" of its results, either directly or indirectly, in particular, through transfer or licensing by:
 - Using them **in further research activities** (outside the action)
 - Developing, creating or marketing **a product or process**
 - Creating and providing **a service**, or
 - **Using them in standardization activities"**

After deadline **2019-11-29** and according to the identification of received results, the first draft of the "Results Table for WP8" is the following:

No	Result – brief description	WP	Lead Partner	Other partners	Is there an exploitable result? Y/N	Possible exploitation route	A/B/C/D/E/O See NOTE	Deliverable number	Dissemination level	Is there a short paper of Deliverable? Y/N	Issue a short paper Due date	Comments
A	New circular thermoplastic raw material reinforced with GFRP-waste (agglomerate and compounded granules)	WP3	CONENOR	AIMPLAS	Y	License to Conenor process patent (pending) and technical consultancy	D/E	D3.1	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	N	M45	AIMPLAS performing compounding trials on Conenor produced agglomerates
B	Developed a natural fiber reinforced polypropylene long fiber thermoplastic pellets for injection molding applications	WP3	NTT	COVENTIVE COMPOSITES, MAIER, CRF, MICROCAB, TECNARO, AIMPLAS	Y	Material can be sold to customers after its use is validated by trials performed at MAIER and CRF during the ECOBULK project. Aesthetics and re-usability of the material is attractive for automotive applications and can also be exploited	A, B, C, E	D3.1	Confidential	N	M45	
C	Developed a new manufacturing process to produce long fiber thermoplastic compounds based on discontinuous and cost-effective fibers	WP3	NTT	COVENTIVE COMPOSITES, MAIER, CRF, MICROCAB, TECNARO, AIMPLAS	Y	Manufacturing process can be used to produce compounds based on recycled fibres as well, thus contributing to a closed loop economy	D, E	D3.1	Confidential	N	M45	
D	Formulations based on sustainable raw materials. Developed compounds for aesthetic and structural automotive parts. Recyclability tests. Compounds based on recycled materials	WP3	TECNARO		Y	Development and production of compounds for automotive plastic parts to be sold to existing customers (here: Fiat and Maier).	A, B, C	D3.1	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	N	M45	
E	Extruded circular single- and multilayer thermoplastic composite profiles and panels reinforced with GFRP-waste	WP4	CONENOR	LIPOR, FCBA, EXERGY, CNR	Y	License to Conenor product patent (pending) and technical consultancy	D/E	D4.2 / D4.4	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	N	M45	CNR performing lab testing on Conenor produced products, other partners demonstrating
F	Automotive parts for aesthetic interior applications made of recycled thermoplastic reinforced compounds by injection moulding processes	WP4	MAIER		Y	Design, development and production of automotive plastic parts to be sold to existing customers.	B	D4.5	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	N	M45	
G	Up-grading plastic quality from automotive sector waste	WP5	BELLVER	TOMRA	Y	Dismantling methods and protocols	C/A	D5.2?	Public	N	M36	Continue research to make a technically and economically competitive process to supply present plastic with higher value within a circular economy context
H	Product tracking and labelling system.	WP6	ITENE	-	Y	Track&trace system standard/protocol and methodology for reverse logistics in circular economies. To apply for different industrial sectors See (*)	C/E	D6.2	Public	N		Possibility of developing and implementing this protocol (traceability) in different industrial sectors, in order to define more cost-effective reverse logistics chains in circular economies

(*) Comments from ITENE: From our point of view, this system is incapable of being patented since it does not develop new technologies or product. Conversely, it implements/applies an existent technology, frequently used in forward logistics, in reverse logistics in order to provide more transparency to a circular business model.

E.3 Summary of received proposals

This table shows the collection data for the received proposals:

	Propose A CONENOR	Propose B NTT	Propose C NTT	Propose D TECNARO	Propose E CONENOR	Propose F MAIER	Propose G BELLVER	Propose H ITENE
Associated Deliverable	D3.1	D3.1	D3.1	D3.1	D4.4	D4.5	D5.2	D5.3
Leader (Deliverable)	NETCOMPOSITES	NETCOMPOSITES	NETCOMPOSITES	NETCOMPOSITES	CONENOR	MAIER	ARN HOLDING BV	TS
Deliverable Type: Report	√	√	√	√	NO	NO	√	√
Dissemination level: Public	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	√	√
Due date of Deliverable	M18	M18	M18	M18	M18	M45	M36	M18
Due date of proposal	M45	M??	M??	M45	M45	M45	M36	M24
Due date within deadline of ECOBULK	NO	??	??	NO	NO	NO	√	√
Scope: Guidelines, recommendations, methodologies, best practices (*)								
No dependency on external tools								
Minimum efforts for conversion into a CWA								
Majority of the partners participating								
Wide potential audience								
(*) Note that safety aspects are excluded, see CEN Guide 29, 4.6								

This summary presents Deliverables found relevant for the ECOBULK project and which can be proposed for transformation into a CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA). This will be included as part of the standardization activities of the project.

Annex F – Roadmap for the standardization process

F.1 What about the roadmap for the standardization process?

The start point is the current standards and the results of ECOBULK Project. Regarding the first deliverables of ECOBULK, and depending on the works of the TC, three different scenarios can be foreseen, based on the expected reaction from CEN standardization bodies regarding a potential standardization proposal coming from the ECOBULK project:

- Negative position of TCs to develop a new document under his work program
- There is already a standard under development in a TC
- Favourable position of TCs to develop a new document under his work program

These three scenarios could be linked to these following cases:

- Impossible to develop future standards, (i.e., there is not Technical Committee)
- Proposal to the relevant TC for inclusion of ECOBULK criteria in the standard under development and ECOBULK participation in the development of the work
- Establish a WORKSHOP to propose of new document (CWA or TR) led by ECOBULK partner and UNE Secretariat, and other project partners. The success and the rate of progress of this document will depend on the facility to achieve consensus with interested European stakeholders, external to the project, also involved in its development.

F.2 What is next on the roadmap for the standardization process?

Development of a more specific roadmap for standardization considering further outputs of ECOBULK to obtain a more advanced and reliable ways for standardization.

Note that there are several types of documents developed by the European standardization system that are in general denominated standards, but that have different characteristics and advantages.

CWA and TR are the best fitted documents to **introduce the outputs of research projects into the standardization system** when this activity is developed as part of the project, due to time considerations and considering them as a first step to be promoted to future standards if their application in the market is successful. The internal regulations of CEN shall be observed for the creation and approval, which usually will take a few months of the decision process.

Another way to disseminate the results of the Project in the framework of standardization is to make recommendations on existing standards and draft standards that cover the same application as ECOBULK research.

At the end of this assessment, we should be getting the following:

- **Negative position of TC to develop a new document under his work program:**
It is a **favorable scenario** to ECOBULK leads new document:
- **Establish a WORKSHOP** to propose of new document (CWA) led by ECOBULK. WS Chair/Technical leader and UNE Secretariat and other project partners will be part of this **Workshop** and the future document will be developed by consensus with external European stakeholders
- **Technical leader and several partners ready to develop CWA.**

Annex G – CWA published- ECOBULK project

G.1 CWA 17806:2021- Design Circular Framework Setting. Composite recovery design solutions in the automotive industry

CEN	CWA 17806
WORKSHOP	October 2021
AGREEMENT	

ICS 13.030.50; 43.020

English version

Design Circular Framework Setting - Composite recovery design solutions in the automotive industry

This CEN Workshop Agreement has been drafted and approved by a Workshop of representatives of interested parties, the constitution of which is indicated in the foreword of this Workshop Agreement.

The formal process followed by the Workshop in the development of this Workshop Agreement has been endorsed by the National Members of CEN but neither the National Members of CEN nor the CEN-CENELEC Management Centre can be held accountable for the technical content of this CEN Workshop Agreement or possible conflicts with standards or legislation.

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EUROPEAN COMMITTEE FOR STANDARDIZATION
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EUROPÄISCHES KOMITEE FÜR NORMUNG

CEN-CENELEC Management Centre: Rue de la Science 23, B-1040 Brussels

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CWA 17806:2021 (E)

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CWA 17806:2021 (E)**European foreword**

This CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA 17806:2021) has been developed in accordance with the CEN-CENELEC Guide 29 "CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreements – A rapid prototyping to standardization" and with the relevant provisions of CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations – Part 2. It was approved by a Workshop of representatives of interested parties on 2021-01-12, the constitution of which was supported by CEN following the public call for participation made on 2020-11-24. However, this CEN Workshop Agreement does not necessarily include all relevant stakeholders.

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- Kawasaki Motor Europe N.V., The Netherlands, Mr Elmo Kaiser, Mr Martin Buitelaar
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CWA 17806:2021 (E)**Introduction**

The concept of circular economy looks beyond the current linear industrial models of “take, make, and dispose”, and instead aims to redefine products and services to design waste out, while also minimizing negative impacts of a linear economy. With scarce resources and an ever-increasing global population, the idea behind circular economy principles is to build long-term resilience, generate business and economic opportunities, and provide environmental and societal benefits.

Such an economy is based on a few simple principles, as shown in Figure 1. First, at its core, a circular economy aims to design out waste. Waste does not exist products are designed and optimized for a cycle of disassembly and reuse. These tight component and product cycles define the circular economy and set it apart from disposal and even recycling, where large amounts of embedded energy and labour are lost. Second, circularity introduces a strict differentiation between consumable and durable components of a product. Unlike today, consumables in the circular economy are largely made of biological ingredients or ‘nutrients’ that are at least non-toxic and possibly even beneficial, and can safely be returned to the biosphere, either directly or in a cascade of consecutive uses. Durables such as engines or computers, on the other hand, are made of technical nutrients unsuitable for the biosphere, such as metals and most plastics. These are designed from the start for reuse, and products subject to rapid technological advance are designed for upgrade. Third, the energy required to fuel this cycle should be renewable by nature, again to decrease resource dependence and increase systems resilience (to oil shocks, for example)¹.

¹) World Economic Forum. Web: <http://reports.weforum.org/toward-the-circular-economy-accelerating-the-scale-up-across-global-supply-chains/from-linear-to-circular-accelerating-a-proven-concept/#view/fn-12>

CWA 17806:2021 (E)

1 Scope

This document tries to set design requirements that make composite products and materials in the automotive sector more easily repairable and longer lasting. Besides, it will ensure that the materials and components of a product can be more easily re-used, refurbished, and recycled, and finally, it will ensure that products are free of hazardous or problematic substances, which can hamper re-use or recycling efforts. In this sense, in this context, the most important addressed are customer perspective, health and environmental impacts and benefits and technical requirements.

2 Normative references

The following documents are referred to in the text in such a way that some or all their content constitutes requirements of this document. For dated references, only the edition cited applies. For undated references, the latest edition of the referenced document (including any amendments) applies.

EN 15344:2007, *Plastics — Recycled Plastics — Characterisation of Polyethylene (PE) recyclates (prEN 15344 under development)*

EN 15346:2014, *Plastics — Recycled plastics — Characterization of poly (vinyl chloride) (PVC) recyclates*

EN 45553:2020, *General methods for assessment of the ability to remanufacturing energy-related products*

BS 8887-2:2009, *Design for manufacture, assembly, disassembly, and end-of-life processing — Terms and definitions*

BS 8001:2017, *Framework for implementing the principles of the circular economy in organizations — Guide*

3 Terms and definitions

For the purposes of this document, the following terms and definitions apply.

ISO and IEC maintain terminological databases for use in standardization at the following addresses:

- ISO Online browsing platform: available at <https://www.iso.org/obp>
- IEC Electropedia: available at <https://www.electropedia.org/>

3.1

business model

an organization chosen system of decisions and activities that determines how it creates, delivers, and captures value over time

3.2

circular economy

a circular economy entails decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resource and designing waste and pollution out of the system. It aims to keep products and materials in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate products and materials at the end of each service life

[SOURCE: Ellen Macarthur Foundation and the UKs Waste Resources Action Program]

G.2 CWA 17807:2021- Dismantling methods and protocols in a Circular Economy Framework. Composite recovery in the automotive industry

CEN	CWA 17807
WORKSHOP	October 2021
AGREEMENT	

ICS 43.020; 13.030.50

English version

Dismantling methods and protocols in a Circular Economy Framework - Composite recovery in the automotive industry

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Ref.No.:CWA 17807:2021 E

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CWA 17807:2021 (E)

Introduction

During the last decades, waste generation has become a serious problem for our highly industrialised societies. "Ensuring the sustainable management of natural resources and wastes" is one of the four priority areas (climate change, biodiversity, health, and resource use and waste), which includes the development of a 'Thematic Strategy on Waste Recycling' and initiatives in the field of waste prevention, notably proposals on European Community waste prevention targets.

These protocols propose a strategy on waste management, which includes a hierarchy of options in which primary emphasis is laid on waste prevention, followed by promotion of preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery.

This goal requires a complete value chain revision. The following steps must be reviewed: design, production, distribution and collection, business models, users, and stakeholder's platform, and, finally, management of waste streams.

At the end of life of circular designed products, new more homogeneous waste streams will allow for more uniform recovered materials to be fed back into the production line. After having studied the circular economy model, waste sorting and characterization technologies as well as material conditioning technologies, as well as minimization, substitution and phase out of chemicals that hamper recycling, its integration as raw materials in production lines, it is time to standardize waste streams managements to close the loop of this circular economy model.

Advanced solutions for collection, sorting and pre-treatments innovations have allowed an increase of more than 5 % the recyclable materials that could be used in current ELVs bulky wastes.

These protocols aim to guarantee an appropriate identification and characterization of incoming wastes and selection of recovered materials after sorting treatment and strengthen this link within chain value working on at least on 95 % of raw materials.

CWA 17807:2021 (E)**1 Scope**

This document overviews, optimizes and validates the strategies and technologies for collection and material recovery (plastics, foam, glass, fibres from vehicle parts) for (re-) manufacturing, in addition to parts that are already being recycled.

Current recycling systems for ELV's are designed to valorize the metallic content. But nowadays, there is an ongoing surge to use non-metallic parts, low value, and complex materials in the vehicle (and future ELV) to reduce their carbon footprint.

2 Normative references

The following documents are referred to in the text in such a way that some or all their content constitutes requirements of this document. For dated references, only the edition cited applies. For undated references, the latest edition of the referenced document (including any amendments) applies.

EN ISO 1043, (serie), *Plastics — Symbols and abbreviated terms*

DIN 6120:2019, *Marking of packaging and packaging materials — Plastics packaging and packaging materials*

VDA 260:2007, *Components of motor vehicles — Marking of material*

SAE J1344:2017, *Marking of Plastic Parts*

3 Terms, definitions, and abbreviations**3.1 Terms and definitions**

For the purposes of this document, the following terms and definitions apply.

ISO and IEC maintain terminological databases for use in standardization at the following addresses:

- ISO Online browsing platform: available at <https://www.iso.org/obp>
- IEC Electropedia: available at <https://www.electropedia.org/>

3.1.1**circular economy**

economy that is restorative and regenerative by design, and which aims to keep products, components and materials at their highest utility and value at the times, distinguishing between technical and biological cycles

Note 1 to entry: A circular economy follows the European waste hierarchy and builds upon four principles: 1. Sobriety, 2. Durability at the heart of all the products, processes, and services, 3. High value retention and high 'loopability' of materials, 4. Out designing of substances of concern and hazardous substances.

3.1.2**reuse**

process by which a product or its parts, which are not waste, are used again for the same purpose for which they were conceived

[SOURCE: Adapted from EU Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC article 3.13]

3.1.3**repair**

process of returning a faulty product to a condition where it can fulfil its intended use

References

For the elaboration of this report, the following sources have been consulted:

- CEN Website (www.cen.eu)
- CENELEC Website (www.cenelec.eu)
- CEN/CENELEC Projex Online database (projex.cen.eu) (restricted to authorized users)
- ETSI Website (www.etsi.org)
- ISO Website (www.iso.org)
- ISO Project Portal (isotc.iso.org) (restricted to authorized users)
- IEC Website (www.iec.ch)
- EUR-Lex (eur-lex.europa.eu)
- European Commission Mandate database (ec.europa.eu/enterprise/standards_policy/mandates/database)
- European Commission Energy website (ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency)
- ISO/IEC/ITU Common Patent Policy (https://isotc.iso.org/livelink/livelink/fetch/2000/2122/3770791/Common_Policy.htm?nodeid=6344764&vernum=-2)